

A NEURAL NETWORK BASED BAYESIAN METHOD FOR ESTIMATING AND PREDICTING RESIN FLOW IN RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is widely used to manufacture composite materials, where maintaining control over resin flow is crucial to avoid defects such as dry spots and voids that can compromise structural integrity. We introduce a Bayesian framework specifically designed to predict race tracking effects in RTM, which result from unpredictable high-permeability channels formed during the manufacturing process. By integrating Bayesian inference with pressure sensor data collected during resin injection, we estimate race tracking strength with uncertainty, enabling predictions of resin flow behavior under varying race tracking conditions.

Although Bayesian inference offers valuable insights for race-tracking prediction, the computational demands of RTM simulations present a challenge, particularly for real-time applications. To address this, a neural network surrogate model is introduced to approximate the complex, discontinuous behavior of RTM simulations caused by race tracking. This surrogate model accurately captures the resin flow patterns generated by traditional finite element-control volume (FECV) methods, enabling significantly faster computations within the Bayesian framework. We demonstrate that utilizing a neural network surrogate within the Bayesian framework can accurately predict both race tracking strengths and non-homogeneous permeability fields in a preform. This integrated approach enables real-time monitoring and control, supporting adaptive RTM systems that respond dynamically to variations in race tracking and produce higher-quality composite products. The findings contribute to the optimization of the RTM process, offering a pathway to reduce manufacturing defects and increase reliability in composite material production.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is widely used in industrial applications due to its relatively rapid production cycle and straightforward experimental setup, which enables the production of parts with shapes close to their final form. However, the production of complex parts is limited by the resin filling stage. This stage is particularly critical for simulation efforts, as it involves careful planning of the injection and venting layout to ensure complete impregnation of the preform and to avoid air entrapment. Trapped air pockets become voids after curing, compromising the composite's structural integrity. For composite parts with complex geometries, this becomes increasingly difficult.

Although simulation tools can be used to design mold injection sites and exit vents, theoretically ensuring complete resin impregnation, there is variability in resin movement. The permeability of the reinforcement primarily influences these deviations. Permeability is typically measured through experiments or estimated numerically [1] [2], and assumed to be constant through the reinforcement and between different preform samples. In reality, the permeability in the preform will vary due to variations or issues in the manufacturing process or draping. In some cases, the inaccurate lay-up of the fabric can

result in regions of lower fiber density on certain edges of the mold, which can act as high-permeability *race tracks* [3] [4] [5]. Race tracks can also be created at bends within the mold.

This research aims to predict the spatially varying permeability of the preform based on pressure measurements made during fill time. This is an inverse modelling problem, which we choose to tackle using Bayesian inference. Bayesian inference provides a principled approach to inverse problems, such as permeability estimation, by incorporating uncertainty directly into the modeling process. We consider both the prediction of only race tracking strengths, modelling the rest of the preform as a homogeneous field, and the prediction of a more general spatially varying field.

2 BAYESIAN INFERENCE IN RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

We now briefly describe the mathematical model used to describe the resin impregnation stage of RTM. We then explain how this model can be integrated into the Bayesian framework for estimating permeability.

2.1 Mathematical Model

Darcy's law adequately describes the flow of resin through a porous medium [6] [7] [4] [8] [9] [10] [11]:

$$q(x, t) = -\frac{K(x)}{\mu} \nabla p(x, t), \quad (1)$$

where x is a vector denoting position, q is the resin flux vector, p is the pressure, μ is the fluid viscosity, K is the permeability tensor and t is time. Assuming that the flow is quasi-static, conservation of mass gives:

$$\nabla \cdot q(x, t) = 0. \quad (2)$$

The volume of resin is modelled with a fixed pressure of $p = p_{in}$ at the injection sites, and $p = 0$ at any exit vents, along with the moving flow front. Where the resin reaches the mold walls, impermeable slip boundaries ($q(x, t) \cdot n(x) = 0$) are enforced. The following model applies only to the region of the mold where resin is present. For the remainder of the dry mold, the pressure is fixed at $p = 0$.

2.2 Computational Model

The most common method for simulating this process is the Finite Element-Control Volume (FECV) method [12] [7] [8] [13] [14] [15] [16]. This method employs a typical finite element mesh to solve for the pressure distribution. Offset from those finite elements are control volumes, which monitor the saturation of the preform. After the pressure is solved, the flow between control volumes can be computed, and the saturation of incompletely filled control volumes can be updated.

2.3 Bayesian Inference

The Bayesian approach to inverse problems is widely adopted, as it provides a systematic means of incorporating and quantifying uncertainty. We are considering an inverse problem with an additive error model, where we attempt to estimate parameters x (in this case, a parameterization of the permeability) from measurements y (in this case, pressure measured from discrete sensor locations during fill time). In the Bayesian framework, the solution to the inverse problem is the posterior probability density (or simply *the posterior*) $\pi(x|y)$, i.e. the conditional distribution of x given y . For in-depth discussions on the Bayesian approach, see [17] [18] [19], among many.

Bayes' formula allows us to express the posterior as

$$\pi(x|y) \propto \pi(x)\pi(y|x) \quad (3)$$

where $\pi(y|x)$ is the likelihood function and $\pi(x)$ is the prior distribution on the parameters x . We suppose that the collected data and parameters of interest are linked by a setup of the form

$$y = f(x) + e \quad (4)$$

where f denotes a model relating parameters to outputs of interest and e denotes a measurement error, which signifies noise present in experimental measurements. We assume a Gaussian distribution for this error term $e \sim N(0, \Gamma_e)$. In this case, the likelihood $\pi(y|x)$ can be expressed as

$$\pi(y|x) = \pi_e(y - f(x)) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|L_e(y - f(x))\|_2^2\right) \quad (5)$$

where $L_e^T L_e = \Gamma_e^{-1}$. We also postulate a Gaussian distribution for the prior $\pi(x) \sim N(x_0, \Gamma_x)$, which mathematically can be written

$$\pi(x) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|L_x(x_0 - x)\|_2^2\right) \quad (6)$$

where $L_x^T L_x = \Gamma_x^{-1}$. Based on the above expressions for the prior (Equation (6)) and the likelihood (Equation (5)), the posterior can be expressed through Equation (3) as

$$\pi(x|y) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|L_e(y - f(x))\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2}\|L_x(x - x_0)\|_2^2\right) \quad (7)$$

A variety of approaches exist for characterizing the posterior for a given problem. For nonlinear inverse problems involving expensive-to-evaluate forward models (as is the case here), high-dimensional parameters, and/or a need for rapid results, fully characterizing the posterior presents a challenge. Complete characterization using methods such as Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) is generally infeasible. In such cases, one approach would be to take the Laplace approximation [20]. Here, we use optimization methods such as Gauss-Newton to find the value of x that maximizes $\pi(x|y)$. This is termed the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate, x_{MAP} . Once this is known, we can linearize $f(x)$ about x_{MAP} with a Taylor series expansion:

$$f(x) \approx f(x_{MAP}) + F_{MAP}(x - x_{MAP}), \quad F_{MAP} = \left.\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right|_{x=x_{MAP}}. \quad (8)$$

Substituting this expression into Equation (7) gives $\pi(x|y) \approx N(x_{MAP}, \Gamma_{post})$, with $\Gamma_{post} = (F_{MAP}^T \Gamma_e^{-1} F_{MAP} + \Gamma_x^{-1})^{-1}$.

3 NEURAL NETWORK SURROGATES

The use of a surrogate model - one that closely approximates the actual process but runs significantly faster - is driven by two key advantages in our application. First, the FECV model within LIMS is highly computationally intensive: every time the moving flow-front boundary changes, it must re-solve the entire FEM problem. By replacing this with a lightweight approximation of the permeability–pressure relationship, we can evaluate the posterior distribution in a fraction of the time without sacrificing essential fidelity.

Second, choosing a neural network as our surrogate ensures a smooth, continuous mapping between permeability and pressure. In contrast, the FECV model exhibits parameter-induced discontinuities that hinder accurate posterior inference: its permeability–pressure curve is not reliably characterized [21]. A neural network built with smooth activation functions naturally overcomes these discontinuities, yielding a more realistic and stable posterior estimate.

We now discuss how the inputs and outputs of the NN are defined for our problem. In Section 3.4, we then discuss how the NN is structured and trained. In Section 3.5, we discuss how inaccuracies in the NN can be accounted for in the Bayesian framework.

3.1 Model Inputs – Parameterization 1

In this first parameterization, we assume that the permeability of the preform is homogeneous, apart from the race tracking regions. Each race tracking region i is assigned a strength x_i , which is related to the permeability in that region K_i with

$$K_i = \exp(x_i)K_{bulk} \quad (9)$$

where K_{bulk} is the homogeneous permeability outside of the race tracking regions. Upon $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots]$, we postulate an independent Gaussian prior with mean $x_0 = 2.0$, $\sigma_x = 2.0$, i.e. $\Gamma_x = \sigma_x^2 I$.

3.2 Model Inputs – Parameterization 2

In an alternative and more interesting parameterization, we allow the permeability to vary throughout the mold, with increased variation in the race tracking regions. To parameterize this, we consider an element-wise log-permeability parameter k , defined by

$$K_i = \exp(k_i) K_{bulk} \quad (10)$$

where i is the element number and K_i is the permeability assigned to that element. On k , we postulate a Gaussian prior that encodes a correlation between the permeabilities of neighboring elements and allows for greater variation in the race tracking regions. We achieve this by firstly neglecting the race tracks, and considering a correlated Gaussian exponential squared covariance of the form

$$\hat{\Gamma}_k[i, j] = \sigma_k^2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2l^2} \|x_i - x_j\|_2^2\right) \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_k^2 = 0.2$, $l = 0.015\text{m}$ is a scalar characteristic length that controls the extent of the correlation and x_i is the location of the center of element i . We then encode the increased variation in the race tracks by applying the following transformation:

$$\Gamma_k = W \hat{\Gamma}_k W, \quad (12)$$

where W is diagonal, and defined as

$$W[i, i] = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if element } i \text{ is in a race track} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

In addition, we have a non-zero prior mean k_0 on k , which is zero in a race tracking element and zero otherwise. Sampling from $k \sim N(k_0, \Gamma_k)$ produces permeability strength for every element as required.

To reduce the dimensionality of this parameterization, we take a principal component analysis (PCA) of this prior to represent k as a lower-dimensional x . Use of PCA is a standard approach to dimensionality reduction [22] [23], so we omit the mathematical details here. We have the truncated singular value decomposition of $\hat{\Gamma}_k$

$$\hat{\Gamma}_k \approx V_n \Sigma_n V_n^T \quad (14)$$

where Σ_n is a diagonal matrix containing the first n eigenvalues, ordered by magnitude and V_n is the first n eigenvectors. In the numerical experiments discussed in Section 4.2, we choose $n = 100$.

We then consider the following transformation

$$k = W V_n x, \quad x = V_n^T W^{-1} k. \quad (15)$$

This transformation converts k , which contains the same number of entries as elements in a finite element model, to x - which is only 100-dimensional.

3.3 Model Outputs

Regardless of the choice of model parameterization, we consider the simulated pressures for the model output. To simulate this, we consider fixed pressure sensor locations throughout the mold. We then extract the simulated pressures at those locations, at specific measurement times t . These measurements have an assumed measurement error $e \sim N(0, \Gamma_e)$ associated with them. We postulate the following covariance on e :

$$\Gamma_e = \sigma_{measurement}^2 I + \sigma_{sensor}^2 \text{diag}(\mathbb{1}, \mathbb{1}, \dots) \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is a square matrix of ones, with one row/column for each measurement time. This allows for some independent measurement error, along with a systematic sensor error, applied uniformly to every measurement from a single sensor. We choose $\sigma_{measurement}^2 = \sigma_{sensor}^2 = 2e^{-4}$ for the numerical experiments here.

As with the second permeability parameterization, we have a very high-dimensional output, which presents difficulties for the learning of the NN. As such, we again reduce the dimension of the output using PCA. After generating training and testing data for $f(x)$ using the LIMS model, we consider the fitted Gaussian on those outputs, $f(x) \sim N(f_0, \Gamma_f)$. We then take

$$\Gamma_f = U_m \Sigma_m U_m^T \quad (17)$$

$$f^*(x) = U_m^T (f(x) - f_0) \quad (18)$$

where Σ_m is the first m eigenvalues diagonalized and F_m are the corresponding eigenvectors. $f^*(x)$ now represents a model that produces only m outputs that represent the predicted pressures. For the numerical experiments described here, we choose $m = 100$.

In this reduced data space, we can still create Bayesian posteriors. This is a novel approach we take here, for reasons that we will soon describe. Consider applying a similar PCA transform as in Equation (18) to the data y , starting from Equation (4):

$$U_m^T (y - f_0) = U_m^T (f(x) + e - f_0). \quad (19)$$

We can then define $y^* = U_m^T (y - f_0)$ and $e^* = U_m^T e$, which gives

$$y^* = f^*(x) + e^*. \quad (20)$$

By conducting Bayesian inference with these alternatives to y , $f(x)$ and e , the usual Bayesian equations derived in Section 2.3 still apply, with the respective changes to notation. The significance of approaching the problem in this way is that it allows for the simple integration of the NN into the Bayesian framework, which will only produce outputs in this PCA space, rather than the original data space. In what follows, it will be useful to note

$$\Gamma_{e^*} = U_m^T \Gamma_e U_m \quad (21)$$

3.4 Network Design

The neural network is designed to match the input-output relationship of $f^*(x)$ created by LIMS (and the PCA). While alternative approaches to NN surrogate modelling of a physical process, most notably the physics-informed neural network (or PINN) [24] [25], this approach is chosen for its simplicity. The neural network is minimizing the loss between the NN outputs, which we term $g(x)$ and $f^*(x)$. We generate 100000 samples using LIMS for training, and 10000 each for training and testing.

Figure 1: Neural network surrogate framework

3.5 Bayesian Approximation Error

Using a surrogate $g(x)$ instead of the underlying model (in this case, LIMS) $f(x)$ introduces surrogate approximation error. Approaching this inverse problem within the Bayesian framework enables the systematic incorporation of this error by augmenting the error term. This is referred to as the Bayesian approximation error (BAE) approach. Consider the following definition for the approximation error ε :

$$\varepsilon(x) = f^*(x) - g(x). \quad (22)$$

We postulate a Gaussian on ε , conditional upon x , of the form $\varepsilon \sim N(\varepsilon_{0|x}, \Gamma_{\varepsilon|x})$, where

$$\varepsilon_{0|x} = \varepsilon_0 + \Gamma_{\varepsilon x} \Gamma_x^{-1} (x - x_0) \quad (23)$$

$$\Gamma_{\varepsilon|x} = \Gamma_\varepsilon - \Gamma_{\varepsilon x} \Gamma_x^{-1} \Gamma_{x\varepsilon} \quad (24)$$

These matrices can all be determined by considering the joint Gaussian of x and ε . ε can then be simply incorporated into the Bayesian framework by defining a new total error term $\eta = e^* + \varepsilon$. Combining this with Equation (23) gives

$$y^* = g(x) + \eta, \quad (25)$$

where we can define $\eta|x \sim N(\eta_{0|x}, \Gamma_{\eta|x})$

$$\eta_{0|x} = \varepsilon_0 + \Gamma_{\varepsilon x} \Gamma_x^{-1} (x - x_0) \quad (26)$$

$$\Gamma_{\eta|x} = F_m^T \Gamma_e F_m + \Gamma_\varepsilon - \Gamma_{\varepsilon x} \Gamma_x^{-1} \Gamma_{x\varepsilon} \quad (27)$$

Using this augmented total error term, we can accurately account for both measurement and surrogate approximation errors in our results. It will also be useful to define $L_{\eta|x}^T L_{\eta|x} = \Gamma_{\eta|x}$.

In summary, the expression in Equation (7) expresses $\pi(x|y)$, based on the FECV LIMS model. If we substitute the NN surrogate (considering the problem in PCA space), but don't account for the approximation errors, we have

$$\pi_{NN}(x|y) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|L_{e^*}(y^* - g(x))\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2}\|L_x(x - x_0)\|_2^2\right) \quad (28)$$

where $L_{e^*}^T L_{e^*} = \Gamma_{e^*}$. However, if we incorporate the surrogate approximation error correctly, we have

$$\pi_{BAE}(x|y) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|L_{\eta|x}(y^* - g(x) - \varepsilon_0 - \Gamma_{\varepsilon x}\Gamma_x^{-1}(x - x_0))\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2}\|L_x(x - x_0)\|_2^2\right) \quad (29)$$

4 RESULTS

We now present the results of numerical experiments. Here, we create a theoretical truth for the permeability parameterization x_{ref} , generate synthetic data by running LIMS to create $f(x)$ and add error e , sampled from the error distribution $N(0, \Gamma_e)$. Based solely on y , we then construct or attempt to estimate the posterior $\pi(x|y)$ and compare this prediction to x_{ref} . We consider the two parameterizations, although both use the same geometry, shown in Figure 2. We use a rectangular preform sheet, bent at four positions to create a ridge. The edges of the mold and those ridges act as potential regions of race tracking.

There are two injection sites, as indicated in Figure 2. These injection sites both inject with a fixed pressure of 100kPa. We use the bulk permeability of $K_{bulk} = 1e^{-10}m^2$ a viscosity of 0.2Pa s.

4.1 Race tracking only

When we consider the parameterization of only the race tracking regions, as discussed in Section 3.1, we are estimating only eight parameters. For this relatively low-dimensional parameterization, it is possible to obtain a view of the posterior using LIMS ($\pi(x|y)$). We can then compare this to the posterior produced by the NN surrogate, both with and without the Bayesian approximation error. To do this, we consider the problem marginally. That is, we fix all $x = x_{ref}$ and we then change one component of x between a range of values, evaluating the posterior at each instance. This ‘gridding’ of the posterior is done to visualize the effects of the NN posterior and this methodology but would not work in practice, as knowledge of x_{ref} is needed. The results of this analysis are shown in Figure 3. Note that these posteriors are exact, without any approximation.

Figure 2: Mold geometry for the numerical experiments in this paper. Injection sites are indicated with black stars, and the race tracking regions are indicated in red.

The Bayesian posterior using LIMS ($\pi(x|y)$) is shown in red. This posterior is narrow and incorporates the truth, indicated by the dashed black line. However, this posterior is very coarse. Posteriors of this shape are difficult to discover in higher-dimensional problems. A Gaussian approximation of this posterior would not be an appropriate fit, and finding the MAP estimate will become infeasible in high dimensions using optimization algorithms.

$\pi_{NN}(x|y)$ has a similar narrow range to $\pi(x|y)$, as they use a very similar error model. However, as we have not incorporated the surrogate approximation error, $\pi_{NN}(x|y)$ often is incorrect in the predictions and confident with the incorrectness. When the approximation error is considered, we have $\pi_{BAE}(x|y)$, which is wider to accommodate the larger error term, but always contains the truth within

the range of predictions. In addition, $\pi_{BAE}(x|y)$ is orders of magnitude faster than $\pi(x|y)$ to generate and use, due to the computational speedup of $g(x)$ over $f(x)$.

Figure 3: Prior and posteriors, normalized to a height of one. The x axis is zoomed to better show the shape of the posteriors.

General Field

We now consider the higher-dimensional parameterization described in Section 3.2. With the 100-dimensional parameter x , it is no longer possible to use LIMS to generate the posterior $\pi(x|y)$, or even to fully characterize the BAE posterior $\pi_{BAE}(x|y)$. Instead, we take a Laplace approximation, as described in Section 2.3, computing a MAP estimate and posterior covariance matrix about that estimate. Results from this investigation are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: MAP estimate (top left) vs the truth (top right). The prior uncertainty is shown in the bottom left plot, and the posterior in the bottom right. Injection sites are marked with blue stars, while black dots denote sensor locations.

In Figure 4, we reverse the PCA transform on our estimations to visualize k , the permeability strengths or σ_k^2 in the case of the uncertainty plots. Note the similarity between the MAP estimate and the truth – our algorithm correctly identifies a race tracking region in the center of the left mold boundary and accurately estimates the strength of the race track. It also correctly identifies the increased permeability at the bottom-center of the mold.

In this example, we observe a posterior covariance with much lower uncertainty than in the prior, as expected. As with the prior, there is greater uncertainty in the race tracking regions. The uncertainty is greatest in the corners of the mold and on the right boundary. This result is logical because the resin reaches these regions last, and the permeability there has a minimal effect on the pressures and movement of the resin away from them. We observe reduced uncertainty near injection sites; however, interestingly, there is no correlation between the sensor locations and the uncertainty. Measurements at the sensors are affected by permeability throughout the mold, not just in the vicinity.

To further compare our estimations, we can examine the difference in flow front movement when both x_{MAP} and x_{ref} are simulated, as well as when the permeability is homogeneous. These are shown in Figure 5. When the permeability is homogeneous, as is typically modelled, the resin takes over 50 seconds to fill the mold, finishing in the bottom right corner. However, our MAP estimate and the truth match very closely, predicting that the mold filled in roughly 40 seconds. They also both predict that the resin moves quickly to the bottom left corner of the mold, then races along the bottom of the mold, finishing not in the bottom right corner but uniformly along the right edge.

Figure 5: Flow front visualized, for three different permeability scenarios. Each control volume is colored according to the time it takes to fill that control volume (in seconds).

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We proposed a Bayesian framework for predicting preform permeability based on pressure measurements taken during the RTM filling process. To avoid numerical issues caused by the FECV method implemented by LIMS, which is commonly used to model RTM, we use a neural network surrogate and incorporate the approximation error into our Bayesian posteriors. The NN surrogate has the additional advantage of being incredibly fast to run, whereas the FECV method can be very computationally expensive.

We first demonstrated our methodology for a low dimensional parameterization of permeability, considering the estimation of only the race tracking strengths. Our results showed that a posterior that included the surrogate approximation error ($\pi_{BAE}(x|y)$) could correctly encompass the true permeability within its uncertainty. Neglecting these approximation errors when using the surrogate ($\pi_{NN}(x|y)$) creates precise but inaccurate posteriors that are misleading or erroneous. We next demonstrated the same methodology with a larger parameterization, which considers general variations in permeability throughout the preform, with greater variation in the race tracks. Using 12 pressure sensors distributed throughout the mold, we can estimate an unknown permeability field sampled from the prior with high precision. Using our estimate for permeability, we can accurately predict the resin flow pattern.

The following steps in this research involve using real-time permeability estimates for online control of the resin flow. Our research has shown that accurate estimations of the permeability field can be made with a limited number of pressure sensors and almost instantly, using the NN surrogate. Approaches such as an extended Kalman filter [26] [27] are designed to adapt the classical Bayesian approach into a real-time updating posterior. As the mold is filled, we can use the posterior to consider the range of permeability scenarios that may be occurring and take control action (such as adjusting the pressure at one of the two sensors) to minimize the chance of creating voids within the part.

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